

PRACTICES, CHALLENGES, AND COPING STRATEGIES OF TEACHERS IN DEVELOPING READING COMPREHENSION OF ELEMENTARY LEARNERS IN GENERAL LUNA DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the practices, challenges, and coping strategies of elementary school teachers in developing reading comprehension skills among learners in General Luna District, Division of Quezon. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research employed a concurrent explanatory design, integrating quantitative and qualitative data in examining teachers' practices in four key areas: vocabulary knowledge, text comprehension, finding the main idea, and answering questions. 50 public elementary school teachers responded to the survey questionnaire with open-ended questions where data is analyzed using weighted mean, frequency count and percentage, and Kendall Tau Correlation. The study found that while teachers highly practiced all four reading comprehension strategies, they faced significant challenges, especially in addressing students' concentration issues, limited home reading support, and balancing curricular demands. Teachers adopted several coping strategies, such as integrating multimedia tools, contextualizing lessons, and promoting critical thinking activities to overcome these challenges. Also, statistical analysis revealed significant relationships between teaching practices and challenges, particularly in the areas of vocabulary knowledge and finding the main idea. Text comprehension was also significantly related to student factors. Based on these findings, the study proposed a policy recommendation to enhance instructional support for teachers, focusing on the provision of resources, teacher training, and parental involvement.

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is crucial for academic performance and lifelong learning. It is associated with a learner's success in school and life (Nguyen, 2022). Therefore, educators must use various instructional strategies to meet each student's needs. These approaches include carefully selecting reading materials and employing multiple methods to assist pupils in understanding challenging texts.

In the global academe, Navarrete (2019) states that reading is an essential language skill crucial for students' educational development, offering more than just the ability to decode texts—it is a complex process that connects readers with ideas, fostering deep engagement with the world around them. Moreover, reading presents unique advantages over auditory information consumption, allowing for self-paced exploration and revisiting content for deeper understanding, thus facilitating a more thorough and self-directed knowledge acquisition (Duke et al., 2021) starting from vocabulary, text comprehension, finding the main idea, and answering the questions.

Similarly, in the Southeast Asian region, reading comprehension is the linchpin of the reading process, essential for recognizing words and deeply engaging with and understanding the text, thereby playing a critical role in both academic achievement and lifelong success (Pham, 2021; Nguyen, 2022). Beyond the classroom, comprehension skills are vital for navigating daily information, making informed decisions, and adapting to the professional world's demands (Hwang & Duke, 2020) to mitigate the challenges experienced by teachers. Research by (Duke et al., 2021) validates the importance of strategic reading comprehension instruction for student achievement, emphasizing the necessity of selecting engaging and challenging materials comprehension (Audina et al., 2020).

Similarly, teaching reading comprehension in the Philippines encompasses several challenges and difficulties, highlighted by Ranico et al. (2023), who note students' diverse backgrounds and learning styles as a significant hurdle. This diversity demands differentiated instruction to cater to students' varied literacy levels, linguistic proficiencies, and cultural contexts, requiring teachers to adapt their instructional strategies and deeply understand each student's needs.

Furthermore, Purnamasari (2023) discusses the integration of effective comprehension strategies, which is often impeded by a lack of professional development for educators. Additionally, reading comprehension assessment is fraught with difficulties, necessitating nuanced tools that can measure the depth of understanding and application of strategies beyond mere recall of facts (Ranico et al., 2023).

Likewise, in DepEd, the country made its debut in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) to benchmark its educational system against internationally recognized standards (OECD, 2019a). The country's performance was below the international average, ranking 78th out of 79 countries, with scores of 340 in Reading, 353 in Mathematics, and 357 in Science (OECD, 2019b). The existing educational challenges have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, posing a threat to the future human capital of this generation with anticipated long-term consequences (Schult et al., 2022; Özdemir & Önderöz, 2022) that coping strategies are deemed significant to overcome such hindrances (Ali, 2020).

Locally, General Luna District, Division of Quezon, also faces challenges in teaching reading comprehension across student-related, instructional, and school-related factors. Student-related challenges include diverse backgrounds and learning styles, necessitating differentiated instruction catering to varied literacy levels, linguistic proficiencies, and cultural contexts. Instructional challenges are highlighted by a lack of resources and time, which complicates adapting teaching strategies to each student's needs. School-related factors include the need for professional development to integrate effective comprehension strategies and address the intricacies of modern texts. Additionally, district Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL IRI) results from District Monitoring, Evaluation, and Plan Adjustment (DMEPA) in the last quarter of SY 2023-2024 showed an increased number of learners with frustration levels in the comprehension area, with 5.17% higher than last year, primarily from rural and barangay schools.

Despite the acknowledged importance of reading comprehension and the extensive strategies recommended by educational research, there remains a gap in applying various coping strategies within the General Luna District. This gap is evident in the struggle to adapt teaching comprehension practices such as vocabulary knowledge, text comprehension, finding the main idea, and answering questions with the challenges teachers face regarding student, instructional, and school-related factors. Hence, this study was conducted to bridge this gap by identifying the specific challenges teachers face and the coping strategies they apply in the locale to explore the suitable policy that can be implemented within the constraints of the local educational system.

With the abovementioned scenario, this study's primary objective was to identify and analyze the practices, challenges, and coping strategies of teachers of General Luna District, Division of Quezon. Ultimately, the research aimed to propose a policy recommendation for instructional support and effective intervention based on the findings, which could improve instruction and support for reading comprehension in the locale. This strategy was envisioned to address the specific needs of the General Luna District, considering the unique challenges and opportunities present in the Philippine educational context, to enhance learners' reading comprehension toward academic success and foster lifelong learning among students.

Research Questions

This study investigated teachers' practices, challenges, and coping strategies in developing reading comprehension of elementary learners in General Luna District, Division of Quezon.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the practices of teachers in teaching reading comprehension in terms of:
 - 1.1. vocabulary knowledge;
 - 1.2. text comprehension;
 - 1.3. finding the main idea; and
 - 1.4. answering questions?
2. What challenges do the teachers face in teaching reading comprehension in terms of:
 - 2.1. student-related factors;
 - 2.2. instructional factors; and
 - 2.3. school-related factors?
3. What coping strategies are available to teachers to address these challenges in developing the reading comprehension of elementary learners?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the following?
 - 4.1 Teachers' Practices in Vocabulary Knowledge and the Challenges they faced in Developing Reading Comprehension in terms of different factors.
 - 4.2 Teachers' Practices in Text Comprehension and the Challenges they faced in Developing Reading Comprehension in terms of different factors.
 - 4.3 Teachers' Practices in Finding the Main Idea and the Challenges they faced in Developing Reading Comprehension in terms of different factors.
 - 4.4 Teachers' Practices in Answering Questions and the Challenges they faced Developing Reading Comprehension in terms of different factors.
5. What policy recommendation for instructional support can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study applied both quantitative and qualitative method in the form of sequential explanatory mixed method. According to Subedi (2016), this is a research approach that follows a two-phase process where quantitative data collection and analysis occur first, followed by qualitative data collection and analysis. This method is designed to use qualitative data to further explain or elaborate on the initial quantitative results, providing a deeper understanding of the research findings. The approach is particularly beneficial for studies that require an explanation of statistical results by incorporating participants' insights, experiences, or contextual factors that numbers alone cannot capture

In this study, the Sequential Explanatory Mixed Method was applied by first conducting a survey to gather quantitative data on teachers' practices, challenges, and coping strategies in teaching reading comprehension. The results were analyzed using statistical tools to determine patterns and relationships among variables. Following this, qualitative data were collected through structured interviews with selected teachers to provide in-depth insights into the statistical findings. The integration of these two data sets allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of how instructional strategies, student-related factors, and school-related challenges influence reading comprehension practices, and finally guiding the formulation of policy recommendations.

Research Locale

The research was conducted in General Luna District, within the third congressional district or Bondoc Peninsula of Quezon Province, Philippines. Nestled in the province, General Luna is a picturesque 4th-class municipality that spans 101.02 square kilometers (39.00 sq mi) and is home to approximately 24,804 residents as of 2020.

Additionally, positioned on the Bondoc Peninsula along the eastern coast of Luzon, this locale is celebrated for its unspoiled beaches, lush mountains, and enchanting waterfalls, making it a sought-after tourist destination. General Luna thrives on tourism and agriculture, cultivating rice, corn, and coconut crops and boasting fishing villages along the coastline.

The choice of this locale was motivated by the observed increase in non-readers over a three-year period, as shown in DMEPA results on PHIL-IRI in the district. Additionally, the school heads and reading coordinators reported low literacy rates in most of the schools, which were caused by inappropriate practice in improving the reading skills of the learners.

Research Population and Sample

This study's research population comprised 50 reading and language teachers within General Luna District, Quezon. The group represented the broader spectrum of educators teaching reading and language skills. Population use ensured a more comprehensive approach to determining the needed data from the district. The selection of participants was determined through a non-probability purposive sampling process, ensuring that the chosen individuals were chosen from the criteria of relevant experience and expertise in the subject matter with experience in handling learners with reading challenges.

Moreover, aside from the 50 respondents in the quantitative part, six (6) teachers also participated in the qualitative phase who were selected through purposive sampling technique. They provided data for the qualitative aspect of the study, ensuring that all teachers were represented from small (2), medium (2), and large schools (2). They were chosen because of their expertise in teaching reading comprehension with their engagement in the district literacy intervention and innovations.

The use of a population covering all the elementary reading and language teachers for quantitative and six (6) participants for the qualitative data collection in a two-phased data-gathering procedure provided a holistic understanding of the phenomenon being studied in all variables.

Similarly, the participants of this study were language teachers from the General Luna District, Division of Quezon, selected based on their experience and educational background in teaching reading comprehension.

Research Instruments

Following the sequential explanatory method there will be two sets of research instruments to gather the necessary data. These will be composed of the survey for quantitative phase and the interview for the qualitative phase.

In the quantitative phase, the survey questionnaire was designed to gather data on the practices, challenges faced, and coping mechanisms employed by the reading and language teachers in General Luna District. The questionnaire consisted of structured items addressing specific aspects, including vocabulary knowledge, text comprehension, finding the main idea, and answering question practices, as well as challenges related to student factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors with relevant coping strategies they apply. The items were carefully crafted based on a thorough review of relevant literature and aligned with the study's objectives. Likert scales, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended items were utilized to comprehensively understand the teachers' practices and challenges.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before commencing data collection, the researcher submitted the research proposal to the relevant ethics committee or institutional review board for approval. This step was crucial to ensure that the study adhered to ethical standards and safeguarded the rights and well-being of the participants. Any required modifications or clarifications suggested by the ethics committee were addressed before proceeding.

Additionally, when the research proposal was approved, the researcher prepared a comprehensive letter of consent outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. This was addressed to the DepEd Superintendent, supervisor, and school heads of public elementary schools in General Luna District. The letter also emphasized the voluntary nature of participation and informed the participants about the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. In the case of the quantitative survey, a group consent approach was used, while individual informed consent was sought for further references.

In the data collection, the researcher contacted the 50 selected teacher-respondents. The researcher distributed the survey questionnaires with incorporated open-ended questions. Participants were given adequate time to complete the surveys. After the quantitative analysis of the data from survey results, the conduct of qualitative

phase with the was done with the six (6) participants who were interviewed individually. Furthermore, qualitative data analysis was held through thematic data analysis to process the interview responses.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

A combination of quantitative statistical analysis in descriptive nature and qualitative data analysis was used in this study.

In Statement of the problem number 1, the practices utilized by teachers in teaching reading comprehension skills, specifically focusing on vocabulary knowledge, text comprehension, finding the main idea, and answering questions. These were subjected to **weighted mean** for each practice area to determine teaching practices' overall effectiveness.

Similarly, in Statement of the problem number 2 for the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading comprehension skills, encompassing student-related factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors, the **weighted mean** was also computed. This analysis provided a quantitative assessment of the perceived challenges, with higher weights indicating greater difficulty as reported by the participants.

However, in Statement of the problem Number 3 to determine the coping strategies applied by the teachers considering the identified challenges, **frequency count and percentage** were applied across the different factors.

Additionally, in Statement of the problem number 4 **Kendal Tau Correlation Coefficient** was carefully applied to test significant relationship between the practices and the challenges in teaching reading comprehension and the hypothesis.

Meanwhile, thematic analysis, based on the Clarke and Braun model, was employed to analyze the qualitative data obtained from the interview questions. The thematic analysis of Clark and Braun's model is a qualitative research method used to identify, analyze, and interpret patterns (themes) within data. It follows a six-phase approach, starting with familiarization, where in this study, the researcher analyzed the responses and interview data from the participants word by word anchoring on the research objectives through reading and analysis. Next, the researcher generated the initial codes by systematically labeling significant features of the data. In the third phase, the researcher harmonized the codes to determine the dominating themes through critically grouping related codes and determining their frequencies. These themes were then reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represent the data and have enough supporting evidence. In the fifth phase, the researcher defined and named the unified theme that uniformly articulate supporting qualitative data. Finally, the findings are reported with the dominating theme as the supporting qualitative data after the quantitative presentation quoting the statements of the participants with discussion of themes, insights, and comparison and contrast to findings from other related studies.

Generally, in thoroughly examining the qualitative data, the researcher aimed to provide a nuanced understanding of the relationships between teaching practices and students' comprehension abilities. The same thematic analysis model was also used to analyze the participants' responses regarding the coping strategies to address the challenges to students' reading comprehension that were available to the teachers to address the challenges to be identified.

Hypothesis of the Study

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' practices in vocabulary knowledge and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension (student-related factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors).

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' practices in text comprehension and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension (student-related factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors).

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between teachers' practices in finding the main ideas and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension (student-related factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors).

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between teachers' practices in answering questions and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension (student-related factors, instructional factors, and school-related factors).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. Practices of Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Table 2

Practices of Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Vocabulary Knowledge

No.	Indicators	Frequency							Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Introducing new vocabulary through context clues	18	26	4	2	0		4.20	Highly Practiced	
2.	Using word maps for vocabulary development	9	27	12	2	0		3.86	Highly Practiced	

3.	Implementing word walls in the classroom	11	13	11	13	2	3.36	Moderately Practiced
4.	Conducting vocabulary quizzes	11	25	11	2	1	3.86	Highly Practiced
5.	Assigning vocabulary journals	1	19	19	7	4	3.12	Moderately Practiced
6.	Incorporating vocabulary games	12	24	11	3	0	3.90	Highly Practiced
7.	Utilizing flashcards for vocabulary	28	16	5	1	0	4.42	Very Highly Practiced
8.	Encouraging the use of dictionaries	15	22	10	1	2	3.94	Highly Practiced
9.	Facilitating peer vocabulary teaching	13	22	9	3	3	3.78	Highly Practiced
10.	Assigning context-based vocabulary exercises	10	29	7	4	0	3.90	Highly Practiced

Composite Mean 3.83 **Highly Practiced**

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Very Highly Practiced (VHP); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Practiced (HP); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Practiced (NP)

Table 2 presents the teachers' practices in teaching reading comprehension in terms of vocabulary knowledge. The findings revealed that the composite mean score for all indicators is 3.83, which falls under "highly practiced." This implies that teachers generally engage in effective practices to enhance their learners' vocabulary knowledge.

Additionally, among the indicators, the top three with the highest mean scores are "utilizing flashcards for vocabulary," with a mean of 4.42, interpreted as "very highly practiced", "introducing new vocabulary through context clues," having a mean of 4.20, described as "highly practiced," and "encouraging the use of dictionaries" with the mean of 3.94 interpreted as "highly practiced." On the other hand, the lowest mean score was observed for the indicator "assigning vocabulary journals," which gained a mean of 3.12 and was interpreted as "moderately practiced". This implies that while teachers recognize the value of vocabulary journals, they are less frequently implemented than other strategies. Possible reasons for this include time constraints or a preference for more interactive approaches like games and flashcards.

The findings indicate that teachers prioritize interactive and contextual methods like flashcards and games to support vocabulary development. The high practice of using

these tools suggests that they are perceived as effective in engaging students and enhancing retention. On the other hand, the lower practice of assigning vocabulary journals may be due to the additional effort required for both students and teachers to maintain and review these journals. For schools, these findings emphasize the need for resources that support interactive learning environments, such as providing ample materials for flashcards and games. For teachers, the results imply a focus on practices that actively engage students, but there may also be an opportunity to explore ways to integrate vocabulary journals more effectively. Lastly, for learners, the high reliance on interactive tools means that vocabulary learning is likely an engaging and stimulating process. Still, additional support could be offered for reflective practices like journaling, which can further deepen vocabulary understanding.

Similar to the study's findings, the research of Jensen (2021) also found that equitable reading instruction requires integrating vocabulary knowledge with reading skills, sociocultural practices, and students' identities. Brandt et al. (2021) noted that teachers who teach both the skill and the love of reading lay the foundation for lifelong reading, though building motivation for reading is often overlooked. In contrast, Pressley et al. (2023) advocate using research-based practices that support all aspects of reading, not just skill development. Moreover, Smith et al. (2023) emphasized that grasping teachers' beliefs and classroom actions is essential for informing teacher training, policymaking, and fostering a shared understanding of effective teaching strategies in schools.

Similarly, Qualitative data from the 6 language teachers' interviews were transcribed and analyzed thematically. Familiarizing data was conducted followed by generating initial codes, searching themes, reviewing themes and naming themes to identify recurring patterns. Majority of the participants revealed that dominating theme "**Routine**" where the participants mentioned:

Participant A: "... you will notice that your learners will be able to remember vocabulary words if the flashcards are used consistently."

Participant B: "By giving them words at least 10 every day. Let them read the words repeatedly, use them in sentences until they become familiar with those words."

Participant C: "Every morning before the lesson introduced to the learners, I gave them different vocabulary words that are not familiar to them."

Participant D: "As a teacher, I help children enhance their vocabulary skills through various teaching approaches, such as the 'Word of the Day,' where I introduce unfamiliar words and explain their meanings."

The qualitative data revealed that routine plays a critical role in vocabulary instruction, as teachers consistently incorporate structured and repetitive strategies to enhance students' word retention and comprehension. Participant A emphasized the effectiveness of using flashcards and visual aids consistently, which reinforces vocabulary learning through repeated exposure. Similarly, Participant B highlighted the

significance of daily word repetition and sentence application, reinforcing the idea that consistent exposure strengthens memory and comprehension. Participant C further supported this by noting that introducing new words before lessons builds familiarity, ensuring that students gradually expand their vocabulary knowledge through structured pre-lesson activities. Beyond structured routines, Participant D mentioned embedding vocabulary instruction within daily lessons through strategies like the "Word of the Day" approach, allowing students to encounter and internalize new words in different contexts. These findings indicate that routine-based vocabulary instruction fosters a systematic and reinforced approach to vocabulary acquisition, which enhances students' overall reading comprehension abilities.

Furthermore, these findings highlight the importance of deliberate and structured routines in vocabulary instruction in reading comprehension development. Teachers must adopt evidence-based strategies, such as repetition, visual aids, and contextual vocabulary learning, to ensure that students acquire and retain new words effectively. Additionally, embedding vocabulary across multiple subject areas ensures that students engage with words in varied and meaningful contexts, promoting deeper comprehension and long-term retention. Schools may benefit from implementing consistent vocabulary programs that reinforce word exposure through daily activities, such as interactive word games, guided discussions, and structured reading exercises. Furthermore, encouraging students to define and use words in their own terms fosters active engagement and cognitive processing, leading to more meaningful and personalized learning experiences. The results suggest that vocabulary instruction should be integrated as a continuous and engaging process in routine, rather than being treated as an isolated or passive learning activity.

The findings of this study align with prior research emphasizing structured vocabulary instruction as a foundation for literacy development. Jensen (2021) underscores the effectiveness of explicit vocabulary teaching combined with comprehension strategies, which mirrors the routine-based approaches observed in this study. Similarly, Brandt et al. (2021) assert that teachers who incorporate both structured repetition and contextual learning create an optimal environment for vocabulary acquisition and long-term retention that must be considered in teaching comprehension in reading.

However, Pressley et al. (2023) caution against relying solely on rote memorization techniques, advocating instead for holistic instructional approaches that integrate vocabulary learning with broader reading comprehension strategies. This perspective aligns with Smith et al. (2023), who highlights that pre-lesson vocabulary exposure and structured repetition help prevent reading difficulties, supporting the study's findings on the significance of consistent word exposure. Overall, the results confirm that effective vocabulary instruction should balance structured repetition, contextual exposure, and active engagement, reinforcing the idea that vocabulary learning is most effective when integrated seamlessly into daily instructional routines.

Table 3

Practices of Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Text Comprehension

No.	Indicators	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Encouraging summarizing passages	7	17	12	13	1	3.32	Moderately Practiced
2.	Discussing story elements	20	24	5	1	0	4.26	Very Highly Practiced
3.	Engaging in read-aloud sessions	24	22	2	2	0	4.36	Very Highly Practiced
4.	Using graphic organizers	18	24	6	2	0	4.16	Highly Practiced
5.	Encouraging prediction before reading	15	26	7	2	0	4.08	Highly Practiced
6.	Facilitating group discussions	13	26	8	2	1	3.96	Highly Practiced
7.	Teaching cause and effect relationships	13	26	9	1	1	3.98	Highly Practiced
8.	Identifying themes in texts	11	27	9	3	0	3.92	Highly Practiced
9.	Discussing the author's purpose	7	30	9	4	0	3.80	Highly Practiced
10.	Using comprehension questions	31	12	7	0	0	4.48	Very Highly Practiced
Composite Mean						4.03	Highly Practiced	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Very Highly Practiced (VHP); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Practiced (HP); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Practiced (NP)

Table 3 shows the teachers' practices in teaching reading comprehension skills regarding text comprehension. The results show that the composite mean score for all indicators is 4.03, which falls under "highly practiced." This indicates that teachers

frequently employ effective strategies to enhance the text comprehension skills of their students. Similarly, this primarily involves "using comprehension questions" with a mean of 4.48, verbally interpreted as "very highly practiced," followed by "engaging in read-aloud sessions" with a mean of 4.36, also categorized as "very highly practiced." Additionally, "discussing story elements" received a mean score of 4.26, similarly interpreted as "very highly practiced." These results imply that frequent comprehension questions and read-aloud sessions are key strategies teachers implement to foster students' understanding of texts. Discussing story elements is also highly emphasized, helping learners analyze and understand various narrative components.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "encouraging summarizing passages," which attained a mean of 3.32, verbally interpreted as "moderately practiced." This implies that, although summarization is recognized as an essential comprehension strategy, it is not employed as consistently as other methods. Potential reasons for this may include time limitations or the complexity of teaching summarization, leading teachers to prioritize other instructional strategies.

The research results indicate that teachers emphasize interactive and guided practices, such as comprehension questions, read-aloud sessions, and group discussions, to facilitate the development of text comprehension skills. These strategies are likely perceived as highly effective in engaging students and supporting their comprehension of texts. The relatively lower emphasis on summarization may stem from challenges associated with teaching this skill, which requires higher levels of critical thinking and synthesis. Meanwhile, these results highlight that schools should emphasize the importance of providing teachers with the necessary support to implement comprehension strategies, particularly those involving more independent tasks like summarization.

Like the research results, Desta (2020) and Karbla et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of differentiated instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners, including those with special needs. Additionally, Karbla et al. (2021) stress the importance of pre-reading strategies, visualization, and summarization, which align with the structured reading practices found in the study. This comprehensive approach addresses mechanical reading skills and cognitive processes, fostering a deeper understanding and practical learning.

Moreover, qualitative data from the interviews with the six language teachers in practices in text comprehension were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis. The process involved becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing those themes, and then naming the themes to identify recurring patterns revealed a major theme focusing on "**Question-Based Comprehension**" where the participants mentioned:

Participant A: "... Let the pupils read it and answer the comprehension questions at the end. By doing so, their comprehension will be developed."

Participant B: "I teach comprehension by using a combination of guided reading, questioning strategies, and discussions."

Participant C: "...I first activate students' background knowledge by asking questions to connect new information with what they know."

Moreover, the qualitative data highlights the dominance of question-based comprehension as a key instructional strategy in text comprehension. Participants emphasized that asking students comprehension questions after reading helps develop deeper understanding (Participant A), while incorporating guided reading, questioning strategies, and discussions (Participant B) further reinforces comprehension skills. Additionally, activating students' background knowledge through questioning before reading (Participant C) helps them establish connections between new and prior knowledge, fostering a more meaningful engagement with texts. These findings suggest that question-based comprehension serves as an essential cognitive tool, enabling students to analyze and interpret texts critically rather than passively absorbing information. Also, beyond questioning techniques, teachers also implement strategies such as experiential learning (Participant C), structured guided reading (Participant D), pre-reading predictions (Participant E), and background knowledge activation (Participant F) to create a well-rounded approach to text comprehension.

The results suggest that it is critical to use structured comprehension strategies that engage students in analytical thinking rather than rote memorization. Question-based approaches help students develop higher-order thinking skills by requiring them to make inferences, summarize, and analyze text meaningfully. Teachers should integrate questioning techniques throughout the reading process, such as pre-reading discussions, mid-reading checks for understanding, and post-reading reflection questions, to enhance students' comprehension. Furthermore, incorporating experiential learning approaches, such as role-playing and real-world application of reading content, can help students develop a deeper emotional and intellectual connection to texts. Schools and educators may also benefit from designing structured comprehension programs that emphasize explicit instruction in questioning strategies, ensuring that students develop the critical skills necessary for independent reading comprehension.

Similar with the current study, Hudson (2021) also asserts that reading comprehension is built upon structured instructional strategies that promote cognitive engagement, reinforcing this study's emphasis on explicit question-based instruction. Similarly, Kasper et al. (2020) found that teaching comprehension techniques such as summarizing, predicting, and questioning significantly enhances students' understanding, supporting the role of question-based comprehension in this study. However, while Desta (2020) highlights the necessity of differentiated instruction to accommodate diverse learning needs, the current study primarily focuses on universal comprehension strategies applicable across various student groups. This contrast suggests that while question-based comprehension is highly effective, it should be supplemented with differentiated approaches to meet the needs of diverse learners. Overall, these findings

confirm that effective text comprehension instruction integrates questioning techniques, structured guidance, and experiential learning to cultivate critical reading skills.

Table 4

Practices of Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Finding the Main Idea

No.	Indicators	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Highlighting key sentences in texts	15 24 9 2 0	4.04	Highly Practiced
2.	Teaching topic sentence identification	8 31 8 3 0	3.88	Highly Practiced
3.	Modeling finding main ideas	10 29 10 1 0	3.96	Highly Practiced
4.	Guiding students in outlining paragraphs	10 29 8 3 0	3.92	Highly Practiced
5.	Providing worksheets main idea	7 27 14 2 0	3.78	Highly Practiced
6.	Practicing identification main idea	15 22 11 2 0	4.00	Highly Practiced
7.	Using visual aids to highlight main ideas	21 21 8 0 0	4.26	Very Highly Practiced
8.	Teaching techniques summarization	11 25 12 2 0	3.90	Highly Practiced
9.	Engaging activities in main idea	11 26 11 2 0	3.92	Highly Practiced
10.	Encouraging inferences main idea	7 29 11 3 0	3.80	Highly Practiced
Composite Mean			3.95	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Very Highly Practiced (VHP); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Practiced (HP); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Practiced (NP)

Table 4 depicts the teachers' practices in teaching reading comprehension skills in terms of finding the main idea. Based on the findings, the composite mean score for all

indicators is 3.95, which falls under "highly practiced." This indicates that teachers consistently employ effective strategies to help students develop their ability to identify the main ideas in texts. Moreover, the highest mean scores entail "using visual aids to highlight main ideas," with a mean of 4.26, interpreted as "very highly practiced," followed by "highlighting key sentences in texts," with a mean of 4.04, and "practicing main idea identification" with a mean of 4.00, both of which are verbally interpreted as "highly practiced." These results suggest that using visual aids, highlighting key sentences, and providing opportunities for students to practice central idea identification are among teachers' most frequently employed strategies.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score was observed for the indicator "providing main idea worksheets," which garnered a mean of 3.78, also interpreted as "highly practiced." While still frequently used, this strategy appears slightly less favored than more interactive and hands-on approaches such as visual aids and practicing identification in real-time.

Moreover, the research results indicate that teachers prioritize interactive and visual methods, such as visual aids and highlighting techniques, to support students in identifying main ideas. These practices are effective in helping students focus on essential information within texts. The relatively lower practice of providing worksheets may be attributed to the preference for more dynamic, engaging instructional approaches. Moreover, these emphasize the importance of providing resources like visual aids that enhance students' comprehension of key concepts in schools. However, for teachers, the results imply a reliance on direct instruction and student-centered activities, with opportunities to further integrate reflective tools like worksheets. Lastly, these practices likely result in an active learning environment that promotes critical thinking and engagement with the text. However, additional support through individual tasks such as worksheets could help reinforce these skills of the learners.

Confirming the research results, the findings from Toonder & Sawyer (2021) and Alussaif (2020) emphasize the importance of identifying the main idea to enhance comprehension and memory retention. In both studies, recognizing the main idea helps students organize details and information effectively, supporting critical thinking and allowing for better summarization. Additionally, like in the current study, teaching strategies such as direct instruction, modeling, and think-aloud (Shelton et al., 2021) are highlighted as practical approaches for guiding students in finding the main idea. Both studies also underscore the use of graphic organizers, like main idea webs or charts, to visually connect the main idea with supporting details, which is consistent with the strategies identified in the current research.

Additionally, Qualitative data from the 6 language teachers' interviews were transcribed and analyzed thematically. Familiarizing data was conducted followed by generating initial codes, searching themes, reviewing themes and naming themes to identify recurring patterns. A major theme "**Identifying Key Details**" was revealed from thematic analysis where the participants mentioned:

Participant A: "By identifying the topic and figuring out what is mostly being said about it. It allows them to understand and think critically about what they're reading."

Participant B: "I teach them to look for key sentences, such as the topic sentence, and identify repeated themes or concepts."

Participant C: "I use strategies like identifying key details, analyzing titles and headings, summarizing paragraphs, asking guiding questions, and using graphic organizers to help learners find the main idea..."

Participant D: "I encourage learners to look for repeated ideas or important points throughout the text."

Likewise, the qualitative data revealed that identifying key details is a dominant theme in teachers' instructional approaches to text comprehension. Participants emphasized strategies that help students distinguish main ideas from supporting details, ensuring a deeper understanding of texts. Participant A highlighted the importance of figuring out what is mostly being said to enhance critical thinking, while Participant B emphasized teaching students to identify key sentences and repeated themes. Participant C described using graphic organizers, summarization techniques, and guiding questions to help learners pinpoint the central message in texts, reinforcing a structured approach to comprehension.

Additionally, Participant D noted that recognizing repeated ideas and important points throughout a passage supports students in identifying the main idea more effectively. The analysis further revealed that teachers integrate visual aids, collaborative learning, textual cues, structured summarization, and pattern recognition as essential strategies for enhancing students' ability to extract key information efficiently.

Moreover, the findings suggest that explicit instruction in identifying key details enhances students' ability to analyze and retain essential information from texts. Visual learning strategies, such as graphic organizers and diagrams, provide structured ways for students to grasp complex ideas, making main ideas more accessible. Additionally, teaching students to recognize textual cues, such as topic sentences, repeated words, and structured summaries, helps them engage in critical analysis rather than passive reading. Collaborative strategies, including peer discussions and guided group activities, create an interactive learning environment where students reinforce comprehension by verbalizing and explaining ideas to their peers. Furthermore, pattern recognition techniques assist students in identifying recurring themes across different texts, enhancing both comprehension and long-term retention. These findings indicate that a structured, multimodal approach to main idea identification is necessary to develop independent and proficient readers.

These results align with Alussaif (2020), who asserts that identifying the main idea is crucial for memory retention, allowing students to effectively recall essential details. Similarly, Shelton et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of direct instruction, modeling,

and think-aloud strategies in helping students grasp main ideas, recommending the use of graphic organizers and structured questioning techniques, which are reflected in this study's findings. Moreover, Karbla et al. (2021) stress the importance of pre-reading strategies such as activating background knowledge and predicting key ideas, supporting the textual cue and pattern recognition techniques observed in this research. However, Elleman & Oslund (2019) argue that highlighting key sentences and summarization exercises alone are insufficient for deep comprehension, suggesting that students must engage in more analytical strategies to extract meaning effectively. This contrast suggests that while identifying key details is essential, comprehension should also include active questioning, critical analysis, and varied instructional approaches to ensure well-rounded literacy development among the learners that can also provide as a reliable foundation for their academic performance.

On the other hand, Elleman & Oslund (2019) suggest that highlighting key sentences and summarization exercises are more than essential for helping students extract main ideas, supporting the findings that teachers guide students in finding key sentences and repeated themes in texts.

Table 5

Practices of Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Answering Questions

No.	Indicators	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Prompting students to ask clarifying questions	19	24	6	1	0	4.22	Very Highly Practiced
2.	Practicing question-answer relationships	19	24	6	1	0	4.22	Very Highly Practiced
3.	Encouraging text-based questions	12	29	9	0	0	4.06	Highly Practiced
4.	Discussing literal and inferential questions	12	31	7	0	0	4.10	Highly Practiced
5.	Practicing answering "who, what, when, where"	34	13	3	0	0	4.62	Very Highly Practiced
6.	Asking comprehension questions after reading	34	13	3	0	0	4.62	Very Highly Practiced

7.	Encouraging peer questioning sessions	12	31	2	2	3	3.94	Highly Practiced	
8.	Modeling answering higher-order questions	13	31	2	2	2	4.02	Highly Practiced	
9.	Implementing reading comprehension exercises	18	26	6	0	0	4.24	Very Highly Practiced	
10.	Teaching text evidence citation	16	25	8	1	0	4.12	Highly Practiced	
							Composite Mean	4.22	Very Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Very Highly Practiced (VHP); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Practiced (HP); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Practiced (NP)

Table 5 presents the teachers' practices in teaching reading comprehension skills regarding answering questions. The findings show that the composite mean score for all indicators is 4.22, which falls under the "very highly practiced." This implies that teachers consistently employ strategies to promote effective questioning techniques and comprehension among students. Moreover, the indicators with the highest mean scores are "practicing answering, 'who, what, when, where' questions" and "asking comprehension questions after reading," both with a mean of 4.62, verbally interpreted as "very highly practiced." These results imply that these practices, which focus on essential comprehension skills and reinforcing understanding after reading, are integral components of teachers' strategies.

Additionally, "implementing reading comprehension exercises" received a mean of 4.24, also interpreted as "very highly practiced," indicating that structured exercises designed to enhance comprehension are commonly used in classrooms. Meanwhile, "encouraging peer questioning sessions" garnered the lowest mean of 3.94, verbally interpreted as "highly practiced." Although still widely used, this technique appears less frequently practiced than other strategies, potentially due to the additional effort required for organizing and facilitating peer-to-peer interactions.

The findings suggest that teachers strongly emphasize structured, teacher-led practices such as comprehension questions and reading exercises, which are viewed as highly effective in reinforcing students' understanding of texts. The relatively lower use of peer questioning may be due to time constraints or the need for more direct instruction in comprehension skills. For schools, these findings highlight the importance of providing ongoing support for teacher-led comprehension practices while encouraging the integration of collaborative questioning techniques.

Similar to the research results, related studies showed that answering questions enhances students' comprehension by requiring them to recall, explain, and critically analyze the text (Blything et al., 2020). This process encourages more profound engagement with the material, promoting a more personal connection to the content (Rahayu et al., 2023). Lastly, building vocabulary through explicit instruction and exposure to varied texts is identified as a critical factor in comprehension success.

Likewise, the interview results in answering questions from the 6 participants were transcribed and analyzed through thematic analysis. This process included familiarizing oneself with the data, creating initial codes, identifying potential themes, reviewing those themes, and finally labeling them to uncover recurring patterns. Revealed the dominating theme “**Active Questioning**” where the participants mentioned:

Participant A: "The common style for students to correctly answer the reading comprehension questions is through asking questions. When students ask questions while reading, it helps them engage with the text, clarify any uncertainties, and deepen their understanding of the material."

Participant B: "My common style for students to correctly answer the reading comprehension question. First, I encourage students to read the questions before the passage to know what to look for."

Participant C: "I ask them to rephrase the question and answer in simpler terms to ensure understanding."

Furthermore, the interview from the qualitative data revealed that active questioning is a key strategy in helping students answer reading comprehension questions effectively. Participant A emphasized that asking questions while reading helps students engage with the text, clarify uncertainties, and deepen their understanding. Similarly, Participant B highlighted the importance of reading questions before the passage, ensuring that students know what to focus on before engaging with the text. Participant C noted that rephrasing questions and answers into simpler terms improves comprehension and helps students process information more efficiently. Additionally, other participants pointed out various complementary strategies, including identifying key details, efficient information retrieval, and text-supported answering. These findings indicate that a structured approach combining active questioning, pre-reading strategies, simplified answering, and textual evidence retrieval enhances students' comprehension and ability to respond accurately to reading questions.

The results imply that teachers utilize multiple comprehension strategies to guide students in developing effective answering techniques. Encouraging active questioning fosters deeper engagement, while pre-reading strategies enable students to navigate texts purposefully. Teaching students to identify key details refines their focus, preventing them from being overwhelmed by excessive information. Additionally, simplifying questions and answers helps students articulate their understanding with clarity, ensuring they comprehend the passage fully before formulating responses. Efficient information retrieval strategies reduce unnecessary reading time, allowing students to locate relevant

details quickly and accurately. Furthermore, text-supported answering builds confidence and reinforces comprehension by requiring students to base their answers on textual evidence. These findings further imply that a structured and multi-faceted approach to comprehension instruction is necessary to help students develop critical thinking and analytical skills when responding to reading questions.

These findings align with the study of Diana & Sepyanda (2022), which highlights that introducing different types of questions—literal, inferential, and evaluative—helps students answer comprehension questions more accurately. Similarly, Ballakrishnan & Mohamad (2020) emphasize that interactive strategies, such as quiz games and group discussions, enhance engagement, supporting the importance of simplified answering techniques. Additionally, Rahayu et al. (2023) found that students often struggle with inferential questions, requiring explicit instruction and practice in making inferences, reinforcing the need for pre-reading strategies and textual evidence-based answering. However, while the current study emphasizes structured questioning techniques, some researchers argue that students also need independent reading time without excessive scaffolding to develop autonomous comprehension skills. This contrast suggests that while guided strategies are essential for developing comprehension skills, fostering independent analytical thinking is equally important for long-term reading success.

Part II. Challenges Faced by the Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Table 6

Challenges Faced by the Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Student-Related Factors

No.	Indicators	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Diverse Reading Levels within the Same Classroom	10 28 10 2 0	3.92	Highly Challenging
2.	Limited Prior Exposure to Reading Materials	9 24 12 5 0	3.74	Highly Challenging
3.	Lack of Motivation and Interest in Reading	13 25 9 3 0	3.92	Highly Challenging
4.	Language Barriers and Multilingual Classrooms	6 25 11 7 1	3.56	Highly Challenging

5.	Attention and Concentration Issues	16	25	8	1	0	4.12	Highly Challenging
6.	Limited Background Knowledge of Various Topics	7	33	9	1	0	4.12	Highly Challenging
7.	Varied Learning Styles and Preferences	7	33	5	5	0	3.84	Highly Challenging
8.	Limited Home Support for Reading Activities	26	16	4	4	0	4.12	Highly Challenging
9.	Reading Disabilities and Special Education Needs	11	17	8	14	0	4.12	Highly Challenging
10.	Socioeconomic Disparities Impacting Access to Resources	7	26	9	8	0	3.64	Highly Challenging

Composite Mean **3.91** **Highly Challenging**

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Extremely Challenging (EC); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Challenging (HC); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Challenging (MC); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Challenging (SC); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Challenging (NC)

Table 6 presents the challenges teachers face in teaching reading comprehension skills regarding student-related factors. The analysis of results revealed that the composite mean score for all indicators is 3.91, which falls under "highly challenging." This indicates that teachers frequently encounter significant difficulties related to student-related factors that impact their ability to teach reading comprehension effectively. Moreover, the topmost challenging indicators with the highest mean scores include "attention and concentration issues," "limited background knowledge on various topics," "limited home support for reading activities," and "reading disabilities and special education needs," all with a mean of 4.12, interpreted as "highly challenging." These results indicate that difficulties with maintaining students' attention, the lack of sufficient background knowledge, inadequate support at home for reading activities, and learners with special needs present significant obstacles to students' reading comprehension progress. These challenges, therefore, require considerable effort from teachers to address. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score was observed for "language barriers and multilingual classrooms," which garnered a mean of 3.56, also interpreted as "highly challenging." While still posing a challenge, this factor appears to be slightly less problematic than other issues, potentially due to teachers being more equipped to handle

multilingual environments or because other factors, such as lack of home support or attention issues, present more immediate challenges.

The findings indicate that teachers are heavily impacted by challenges related to students' attention, prior knowledge, and home environment. These factors may limit students' readiness to engage with reading comprehension tasks and require teachers to adopt additional strategies to overcome these barriers. Additionally, the high prevalence of challenges related to home support suggests that schools may need to increase efforts to engage families in supporting students' reading activities. The findings also highlight the need for more resources and teachers' training to manage attention issues and provide background knowledge to learners lacking in these areas. Furthermore, the presence of these challenges underscores the importance of providing differentiated instruction among the learners that can meet diverse needs within the classroom, particularly for students who may face barriers outside of school and learners with unique needs.

Same with the current results, studies also showed that teachers in teaching reading comprehension are addressing the diverse learning needs of students, who come from various backgrounds and have unique requirements, including learning disabilities or limited literacy exposure at home (Schult et al., 2022; Printer, 2021). Additionally, a lack of prior knowledge can hinder students' understanding of texts, prompting teachers to provide extra context or materials (Pressley, 2023). Motivating students to engage in reading is another significant challenge, requiring teachers to make reading engaging and relevant to students' lives (McBreen & Savage, 2020).

Additionally, Thematic analysis was applied to the qualitative data to identify key themes. This process involved becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, identifying possible themes, reviewing them, and ultimately labeling them to reveal recurring patterns. The interview results showed the major theme "**Lack of Motivation and Focus**" on the challenges from participants who mentioned:

Participant A: "The most challenging that I observe among my students that hinder them from effectively reading with comprehension is they lack motivation..."

Participant B: "When it comes to reading comprehension, it is very important that the learner has motivation and attention/concentration to what he/she listens/reads..."

Participant C: "The biggest challenge I observe among the students that hinders them from effectively reading with comprehension is they think they did not do everything...."

Participant D: "Focus attention and other environmental issues. To cope with this challenge, devote extra time and understand every situation."

Participant E: "Learners' ability to remember and focus. To cope with this challenge, individual practice is advised."

Moreover, the qualitative data revealed that lack of motivation and focus is a major challenge that hinders students' reading comprehension. Participant A emphasized that low motivation prevents students from engaging effectively with texts, while Participant B highlighted that both motivation and concentration are essential for successful comprehension. Additionally, Participant C noted that students' lack of confidence in their abilities further affects their engagement, making them feel they are not making progress in their reading skills. Other factors influencing comprehension difficulties include environmental distractions (Participant D), challenges in focusing attention (Participant E), and memory retention. These findings suggest that students struggle with both internal (motivation, attention, and memory retention) and external (home support, environmental distractions) factors, all of which impact their ability to process and understand reading materials effectively.

Findings indicate that teachers must implement engaging and interactive strategies, such as gamified reading activities, storytelling techniques, and peer-assisted learning, to increase student interest and intrinsic motivation. Additionally, structured visual and auditory aids can help students struggling with attention and memory retention, ensuring they remain focused throughout reading exercises. To counteract environmental distractions, schools should create structured reading spaces that minimize disruptions and foster concentration.

Similarly, Pressley (2023) emphasizes that students with limited prior knowledge struggle with comprehension, reinforcing the need for supplementary instructional materials and differentiated learning strategies. However, unlike Merga & Mason (2019), who emphasize developmental differences as the primary barrier to reading comprehension.

Table 7

Challenges Faced by the Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of Instructional Factors

No.	Indicators	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Insufficient time allocated for reading instruction	5	25	18	2	0	3.66	Highly Challenging
2.	Limited Access to Varied and Up-to-Date Reading Materials	5	21	12	12	0	3.38	Moderately Challenging

3.	Inadequate Professional Development Opportunities	7	16	18	9	0	3.42	Highly Challenging
4.	Large Class Sizes Impacting Individualized Instruction	8	14	14	12	2	3.28	Moderately Challenging
5.	Balancing Standardized Test Preparation with Comprehension	9	24	14	2	1	3.76	Highly Challenging
6.	Limited Technology Integration for Dynamic Instruction	6	17	14	13	0	3.32	Moderately Challenging
7.	Lack of Effective Strategies to Address Diverse Learners	7	17	16	10	0	3.42	Highly Challenging
8.	Inadequate Assessment Tools for Monitoring Progress	7	20	13	10	0	3.48	Highly Challenging
9.	Limited Collaboration Time with Peers for Lesson Planning	5	17	19	9	0	3.36	Moderately Challenging
10.	Balancing Reading Instruction with Other Curriculum Demands	10	25	11	4	0	3.82	Highly Challenging

Composite Mean **3.49** **Highly Challenging**

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Extremely Challenging (EC); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Challenging (HC); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Challenging (MC); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Challenging (SC); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Challenging (NC)

Table 7 portrays the challenges teachers face regarding instructional factors in teaching reading comprehension skills. The quantitative analysis revealed that the composite mean score for all indicators is 3.49, interpreted as "highly challenging." This implies that instructional factors significantly affect teachers' ability to teach reading

comprehension effectively. Similarly, the top challenging indicators involved "balancing reading instruction with other curriculum demands," with a mean of 3.82, "balancing standardized test preparation with comprehension," with a mean of 3.76, and "insufficient time allocated for reading instruction," with a mean of 3.66, all interpreted as "highly challenging." These results indicate that teachers experience considerable difficulty in balancing various academic demands, including test preparation and curriculum requirements, with the need to allocate sufficient time for comprehensive reading instruction.

Conversely, the lowest mean score was observed for "large class sizes impacting individualized instruction," which garnered a mean of 3.28, verbally interpreted as "moderately challenging." While still posing a challenge, this factor appears less problematic compared to other instructional difficulties, possibly because teachers may have developed strategies to manage larger classes, or they might prioritize other issues, such as balancing curriculum demands and reading instruction time.

The findings suggest that teachers face significant instructional challenges, particularly when balancing reading instruction with other curriculum demands and standardized test preparation. These time and curriculum pressures may limit the ability to focus on reading comprehension, necessitating more structured support. Likewise, these findings highlight the need to re-evaluate time allocation for reading instruction and provide teachers with resources to manage curriculum pressures effectively. Similarly, the results suggest that professional development focused on time management and integrating reading with other subjects could help alleviate some of these instructional challenges. Finally, providing solutions to these instructional challenges could lead to more dedicated time for reading comprehension activities, potentially improving their academic performance beyond mere reading.

Confirming the current study, other studies also found that the challenges in teaching reading comprehension often stem from instructional limitations, including inadequate teacher training and insufficient access to quality resources (Ranico et al., 2023). Many educators lack proper training in effective reading strategies, leading to difficulties in implementing instructional methods, assessing student progress, and differentiating instruction for diverse learning needs (Kamala, 2022; Kasper et al., 2020).

Additionally, thematic analysis was used to examine the qualitative data and identify key themes. This process included familiarizing oneself with the data, developing initial codes, recognizing potential themes, reviewing them, and finally assigning labels to uncover recurring patterns.

Moreover, the qualitative data from the results revealed the major theme "**Diversity of Learners**" as challenge where the interview mentioned:

Participant A: "The most challenging factor in teaching reading comprehension is addressing the diverse needs and skill levels of students, ensuring each student understands and engages with text effectively."

Participant B: "One of the most challenging factors in teaching reading comprehension is addressing the diverse skill levels and backgrounds of students. Some learners struggle with decoding words, while others have difficulty understanding vocabulary or making inferences..."

Furthermore, the qualitative data showed that the diversity of learners presents a major challenge in reading comprehension instruction, as teachers must accommodate students with varying skill levels, learning backgrounds, and comprehension abilities. Participant A emphasized the difficulty of ensuring that each student engages with the text effectively, particularly when some struggle with basic literacy skills while others can comprehend more advanced material. Similarly, Participant B highlighted that students' difficulties range from decoding words to vocabulary comprehension and inference-making, illustrating the need for differentiated instruction tailored to students' specific needs. These findings suggest that teaching reading comprehension is not a one-size-fits-all process; rather, it requires personalized learning strategies, adaptive instruction, and flexible teaching methods to ensure that all students develop the necessary comprehension skills.

These imply that teachers must implement targeted instructional strategies to address diverse learning needs effectively. One key approach is differentiated instruction, which involves using tiered reading materials, individualized support, and small-group instruction to accommodate students at different proficiency levels. Additionally, scaffolded learning approaches, such as guided reading, explicit vocabulary instruction, and structured comprehension exercises, can provide struggling students with the support they need while allowing more advanced learners to engage with complex texts. Moreover, the study suggests that teacher training programs should emphasize adaptive teaching strategies, ensuring that educators are well-equipped to modify their instruction based on student needs. Schools should also invest in varied instructional resources, such as leveled texts, digital learning tools, and culturally relevant materials.

These findings align with the studies of Kamala (2022) and Kasper et al. (2020), which assert that without proper training, teachers struggle to implement differentiated instruction, assess student progress accurately, and adapt to diverse classroom needs. However, unlike Moswane (2019), who argues that teachers' language proficiency is the primary barrier to reading instruction, the present study focuses on external instructional factors, such as curriculum demands, engagement strategies, and differentiation challenges, as key obstacles. This contrast suggests that while teacher expertise remains crucial in fostering reading comprehension, addressing external challenges through structured support systems, instructional resources, and targeted teacher training is equally essential in ensuring successful literacy development for all students.

Table 8

Challenges Faced by the Teachers in Teaching Reading Comprehension in Terms of School-Related Factors

No.	Indicators	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Insufficient Funding for Reading Programs and Resources	14	14	13	9	0	3.66	Highly Challenging
2.	Curriculum Constraints Limiting Flexibility in Teaching Methods	10	25	13	2	0	3.86	Highly Challenging
3.	Lack of Supportive Teachers for Reading Initiatives	10	13	11	16	0	3.34	Moderately Challenging
4.	Inconsistent Implementation of Reading Programs Across Schools	7	17	13	13	0	3.36	Moderately Challenging
5.	Limited Availability of Professional Development Opportunities for Teachers	7	19	9	15	0	3.36	Moderately Challenging
6.	Standardized Testing Pressure Negatively Impacting Instruction	6	20	17	7	0	3.50	Highly Challenging
7.	Inadequate Time Allocated in the School Schedule for Reading	5	22	17	6	0	3.52	Highly Challenging
8.	Limited Parental Involvement and Awareness in Reading Programs	14	21	13	2	0	3.94	Highly Challenging

9.	Inequitable Distribution of Resources Across Schools	11	13	14	12	0	3.46	Highly Challenging	
10.	Changing Educational Trends Impacting Consistency in Approach	10	17	17	6	0	3.62	Highly Challenging	
							Composite Mean	3.56	Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 = Extremely Challenging (EC); 3.41 – 4.20 Highly Challenging (HC); 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately Challenging (MC); 1.81 – 2.60 Slightly Challenging (SC); 1.00 – 1.80 Not Challenging (NC)

Table 8 comprehensively shows the challenges teachers face in teaching reading comprehension skills regarding school-related factors. The findings showed that the composite mean score for all indicators is 3.56 and interpreted as "highly challenging." This indicates that school-related factors significantly challenge teachers in effectively delivering reading comprehension instruction. Additionally, the challenges with the highest mean scores are "limited parental involvement and awareness in reading programs," with a mean of 3.94, "curriculum constraints limiting flexibility in teaching methods," with a mean of 3.86, and "insufficient funding for reading programs and resources" with a mean of 3.66, all verbally interpreted as "highly challenging." These findings underscore that teachers experience significant difficulties due to a lack of parental involvement, rigid curriculum structures that restrict teaching flexibility, and insufficient financial resources to support reading programs.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score was observed for "lack of supportive teachers for reading initiatives," which garnered a mean of 3.34, interpreted as "moderately challenging." Although still a challenge, this factor seems less problematic than others; this could occur because teachers have adapted to work with existing support systems or have found ways to collaborate with colleagues on their initiatives.

Generally, the results indicate that teachers face substantial challenges related to school infrastructure, particularly inadequate parental involvement, curriculum constraints, and funding shortages. These challenges highlight the need for schools to enhance support mechanisms, allocate sufficient resources, and foster greater collaboration between educators, parents, and administrators. Also, the results indicate that overcoming these obstacles requires adaptability and creative approaches to maximize limited resources and work within existing curriculum frameworks. Addressing these school-related challenges could also create a more supportive and resource-rich environment, enhancing their reading comprehension development and overall academic success.

The results also affirm the related studies where school-related factors significantly challenge teaching reading comprehension skills (Hwang & Duke, 2020). Inadequate teacher preparation and limited professional development hinder teachers' ability to apply the latest reading comprehension strategies and address students' needs (Taladngoan et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the results from thematic analysis showed a dominating theme of **“Curriculum Changes”** in which the participants in the interview mentioned:

Participant A: "Inadequate time allocated in the school schedule for reading hinders me the most in achieving effective teaching when it comes to reading..."

Participant B: "The curriculum, teacher availability, and the effectiveness of the reading program..."

Participant C: "Changing educational trends impacting consistency in approach..."

Moreover, the qualitative data revealed that curriculum changes present significant challenges in reading comprehension instruction, as teachers struggle to adapt to shifting educational policies, time constraints, and resource availability. Participant A emphasized that insufficient time allocated for reading instruction within the school schedule hinders effective teaching, limiting opportunities for in-depth reading comprehension development. Participant B highlighted broader systemic challenges, including curriculum structure, teacher availability, and the effectiveness of reading programs, which influence instructional quality and student learning outcomes. Additionally, Participant C noted that changing educational trends impact consistency in instructional approaches, making it difficult for teachers to maintain structured and continuous reading instruction. These findings suggest that curriculum modifications, when not aligned with effective literacy instruction frameworks, create inconsistencies that disrupt reading development and instructional effectiveness.

The research findings indicate the need for structured curriculum planning and professional development opportunities to support teachers in adapting to changes effectively. Schools should consider allocating sufficient instructional time for reading comprehension within the curriculum, ensuring that students receive consistent exposure to literacy instruction. Additionally, teacher training programs should focus on equipping educators with adaptive strategies to navigate evolving curricular requirements while maintaining effective reading instruction. Furthermore, educational policymakers must consult with educators before implementing curriculum modifications, ensuring that any changes are aligned with best practices in reading comprehension instruction. Schools should also prioritize access to updated instructional resources and reading materials, as outdated or inconsistent materials hinder student engagement and literacy growth.

Similarly, these findings align with Hwang and Duke (2020), who argue that curriculum variability and inconsistent instructional materials contribute to disparities in

reading comprehension instruction, reinforcing the need for standardized and evidence-based literacy frameworks. Similarly, Kiew & Shah (2020) emphasize that teacher preparation and professional development are crucial in ensuring that educators are equipped with effective reading strategies, supporting the present study's call for ongoing training to help teachers adapt to curriculum changes. Additionally, Taladngoen et al. (2020) highlight the impact of limited access to quality instructional resources, noting that outdated textbooks and insufficient reading materials negatively affect student engagement and learning outcomes, which aligns with the challenges reported by teachers in this study. However, in contrast to Moats (2020), who attributes reading instruction difficulties primarily to teacher expertise and training, the present study emphasizes institutional barriers, such as school policies, parental involvement, and resource availability, as key obstacles to literacy development. This contrast suggests that while teacher training is essential, addressing systemic challenges such as curriculum stability, instructional time allocation, and resource accessibility is equally critical in improving reading comprehension instruction.

Part III. Coping Strategies of Teachers in Developing Reading Comprehension of Elementary Learners to Address the Challenges

Table 9

Coping Strategies of Teachers in Developing Reading Comprehension of Elementary Learners to Address the Challenges

Student Related Factors	Coping Strategy	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Diverse Reading Levels within the Same Classroom	1. Implementing differentiated reading groups.	20	40.00	1
	2. Providing leveled reading materials.	18	36.00	2
	3. Using adaptive learning software to individualize instruction.	2	4.00	5
	4. Establishing classroom libraries with diverse materials.	5	10.00	3.5
	5. Connecting reading materials to students' interests.	5	10.00	3.5
	1. Integrating read-aloud sessions to build exposure.	22	44.00	1

2. Limited Prior Exposure to Reading Materials	2. Establishing classroom libraries with diverse materials.	2	4.00	5
	3. Organizing book exchange programs.	3	6.00	4
	4. Providing leveled reading materials.	18	36.00	2
	5. Using multimedia resources to enhance understanding.	5	10.00	3
3. Lack of Motivation and Interest in Reading	1. Introducing student choice in reading selections.	5	10.00	4
	2. Connecting reading materials to students' interests.	10	20.00	2
	3. Implementing reward-based reading programs.	28	56.00	1
	4. Using multimedia resources to motivate learners.	7	14.00	3
4. Language Barriers and Multilingual Classrooms	1. Incorporating bilingual books and resources.	2	4.00	4.5
	2. Using visual aids and gestures to support comprehension.	25	50.00	1
	3. Providing language support through peer tutoring.	11	22.00	2
	4. Building background knowledge through pre-reading activities.	10	20.00	3
	5. Using multimedia resources.	2	4.00	4.5
5. Attention and Concentration Issues	1. Incorporating short, interactive reading activities.	18	36.00	1
	2. Utilizing movement breaks during reading sessions.	5	10.00	4.5

		3. Implementing structured reading routines.	10	20.00	3
		4. Using multimedia resources with new topics.	5	10.00	4.5
		5. Offering multimodal reading activities (audio, visual, kinesthetic).	12	24.00	2
		1. Building background knowledge through pre-reading activities.	20	40.00	1
6.	Limited Background Knowledge of Various Topics	2. Connecting new topics to familiar experiences.	10	20.00	3
		3. Using multimedia resources to enhance understanding.	10	20.00	3
		4. Establishing classroom libraries with diverse materials.	10	20.00	3
		1. Offering multimodal reading activities (audio, visual, kinesthetic).	5	10.00	4
		2. Providing choices in how students demonstrate understanding.	5	10.00	4
7.	Varied Learning Styles and Preferences	3. Designing reading assignments to individual learning preferences.	15	30.00	2
		4. Implementing multisensory reading instruction strategies.	5	10.00	4
		5. Using a differentiated approach in teaching.	20	40.00	1
8.	Limited Home Support for Reading Activities	1. Sending home reading materials and guides for parents.	35	70.00	1
		2. Organizing family literacy nights at school.	1	2.00	4

	3. Creating partnerships with local libraries for student access.	2	4.00	3
	4. Involving parents and guardians in planning reading activities at home.	12	24.00	2
9. Reading Disabilities and Special Education Needs	1. Using assistive technology and tools for reading support.	15	30.00	2.5
	2. Collaborating with special education teachers for individualized plans.	20	40.00	1
	3. Implementing multisensory reading instruction strategies.	15	30.00	2.5
10. Socioeconomic Disparities Impacting Access to Resources	1. Providing free or low-cost access to books and reading materials.	10	20.00	3
	2. Creating partnerships with local libraries for student access.	10	20.00	3
	3. Offering before- and after-school reading programs.	15	30.00	1
	4. Using free multimedia resources.	5	10.00	5
	5. Conduct a book campaign for the learners.	10	20.00	3
Instructional Factors	Coping Strategy	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Insufficient Time Allocated for Reading Instruction	1. Integrating reading activities into other subject areas.	13	26.00	2
	2. Using block scheduling to create longer reading periods.	10	20.00	3

	3. Prioritizing essential reading skills during instruction.	7	14.00	4
	4. Utilizing small group instruction and reading centers.	20	40.00	1
2. Limited Access to Varied and Up-to-Date Reading Materials	1. Leveraging digital libraries and online resources.	20	40.00	1
	2. Partnering with local libraries and community organizations.	15	30.00	2.5
	3. Implementing classroom book-sharing systems.	15	30.00	2.5
3. Inadequate Professional Development Opportunities	1. Participating in online courses and webinars on reading instruction.	5	10.00	5
	2. Forming professional learning communities (PLCs) within the school.	8	16.00	3
	3. Attending educational conferences and workshops.	8	16.00	3
	4. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	21	42.00	1
	5. Attending free or subsidized training/scholarship.	8	16.00	3
4. Large Class Sizes Impacting Individualized Instruction	1. Utilizing small group instruction and reading centers.	19	38.00	2
	2. Implementing peer tutoring and collaborative learning.	23	46.00	1
	3. Using classroom aides or volunteers to assist with reading groups.	8	16.00	3
5. Balancing Standardized Test	1. Integrating test preparation into regular reading activities.	10	20.00	3.5

Preparation with Comprehension		2. Focusing on critical thinking and comprehension skills over rote memorization.	15	30.00	1.5
		3. Aligning reading instruction with test standards without compromising the depth of learning.	10	20.00	3.5
		4. Incorporating multimedia tools and interactive reading software.	15	30.00	1.5
		1. Incorporating multimedia tools and interactive reading software.	10	20.00	3.5
6. Limited Technology Integration for Dynamic Instruction		2. Using online platforms for reading and comprehension practice.	15	30.00	1.5
		3. Providing professional development on effective technology use in reading instruction.	15	30.00	1.5
		4. Using classroom aides or volunteers to assist with reading groups.	10	20.00	3.5
		1. Using differentiated instruction approaches.	15	30.00	1
7. Lack of Effective Strategies to Address Diverse Learners		2. Utilizing universal design for learning (UDL) principles.	5	10.00	5
		3. Providing contextualized interventions and support for struggling readers.	10	20.00	3
		4. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	12	24.00	2
		5. Attending free or subsidized training/scholarship.	8	16.00	4

	1. Using formative assessments to guide instruction.	15	30.00	2
8. Inadequate Assessment Tools for Monitoring Progress	2. Providing contextualized interventions and support for struggling readers.	25	50.00	1
	3. Incorporating technology-based assessment tools for real-time feedback.	10	20.00	3
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	1. Scheduling regular collaborative planning meetings.	15	30.00	2
9. Limited Collaboration Time with Peers for Lesson Planning	2. Using online collaboration tools and shared planning resources.	3	6.00	5
	3. Forming cross-grade level teams for comprehensive planning.	5	10.00	3.5
	4. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	22	44.00	1
	5. Attending free or subsidized training/workshops.	5	10.00	3.5
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	1. Integrating reading instruction across the curriculum.	23	46.00	1
10. Balancing Reading Instruction with Other Curriculum Demands	2. Prioritizing key reading skills and strategies within limited time frames.	8	16.00	3
	3. Implementing interdisciplinary projects that include reading components.	4	8.00	4
	4. Scheduling regular collaborative planning meetings.	15	30.00	2
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School Factors	Related	Coping Strategy	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Insufficient Funding for Reading Programs and Resources		1. Applying for grants for reading programs.	10	20.00	3
		2. Partnering with local businesses and community organizations for donations.	10	20.00	3
		3. Utilizing free or low-cost online reading resources.	10	20.00	3
		4. Requesting for LGU and NGO support.	10	20.00	3
		5. Conducting Fund Generating Activities.	10	20.00	3
2. Curriculum Constraints Limiting Flexibility in Teaching Methods		1. Integrating creative teaching methods within the existing curriculum framework.	10	20.00	3
		2. Advocating for curriculum revisions to include more flexibility.	12	24.00	1
		3. Collaborating with colleagues to share best practices for working within constraints.	10	20.00	3
		4. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	10	20.00	3
		5. Attending free or subsidized training/workshops.	8	16.00	5
3. Lack of Supportive Teachers for Reading Initiatives		1. Building a reading committee to promote collaborative efforts.	15	30.00	1.5
		2. Offering peer mentoring and support programs for teachers.	10	20.00	3.5

	3. Recognizing and rewarding teachers who support reading initiatives.	10	20.00	3.5
	4. Developing a district-wide reading program with standardized guidelines.	15	30.00	1.5
4. Inconsistent Implementation of Reading Programs Across Schools	1. Online sharing or publication of the reading program.	5	10.00	5
	2. Requesting for a memorandum of support for consistent implementation.	10	20.00	3
	3. Conducting regular evaluations and feedback sessions to ensure uniformity.	10	20.00	3
	4. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	15	30.00	1
	5. Developing a district-wide reading program with standardized guidelines.	10	20.00	3
5. Limited Availability of Professional Development Opportunities for Teachers	1. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	8	16.00	3.5
	2. Requesting for LGU and NGO support.	17	34.00	1
	3. Conducting Fund Generating Activities.	7	14.00	5
	4. Requesting scholarship grants.	10	20.00	2
	5. Attending free or subsidized training/workshops.	8	16.00	3.5
6. Standardized Testing Pressure Negatively Impacting Instruction	1. Balancing test preparation with engaging, meaningful reading activities.	15	30.00	1.5
	2. Integrating test-taking strategies into regular	10	20.00	3.5

		instruction without overshadowing content.			
		3. Fostering a classroom environment that values learning over testing.	10	20.00	3.5
		4. Developing a district-wide reading program with standardized guidelines.	15	30.00	1.5
		1. Maximizing available time by incorporating reading into other subjects.	10	20.00	3
		2. Advocating for schedule adjustments to increase reading time.	10	20.00	3
7.	Inadequate Time Allocated in the School Schedule for Reading	3. Implementing reading blocks or rotations within the existing schedule.	10	20.00	3
		4. Using block scheduling to create longer reading periods.	10	20.00	3
		5. Prioritizing essential reading skills during instruction.	10	20.00	3
		1. Hosting parent workshops to educate on the importance of reading.	12	24.00	2
		2. Send home newsletters with reading tips and resources.	8	16.00	4
8.	Limited Parental Involvement and Awareness in Reading Programs	3. Encouraging parents to participate in classroom reading activities.	20	40.00	1
		4. Partnering with local organizations to bridge resource gaps.	10	20.00	3
9.	Inequitable Distribution of	1. Advocating for equitable resource distribution at the district level.	10	20.00	3

Resources Across Schools	2. Sharing resources between schools through a lending system.	12	24.00	2
	3. Partnering with local organizations to bridge resource gaps.	8	16.00	4
	4. Requesting for LGU and NGO support.	20	40.00	1
1. Staying informed about new trends while maintaining proven strategies.		8	16.00	3.5
10. Changing Educational Trends Impacting Consistency in Approach	2. Providing training on integrating new trends with existing practices.	8	16.00	3.5
	3. Conduct local training through SLAC / INSET.	20	40.00	1
	4. Developing a district-wide reading program with standardized guidelines.	14	28.00	2

Table 9 outlines the teachers' coping strategies to address student-related challenges in developing reading comprehension skills among elementary learners. Considering the top-most challenges in student-related factors in "attention and concentration issues," "incorporating short, interactive reading activities" ranks highest, utilized by 18 teachers or 36.00% of respondents to maintain student engagement. To address "limited background knowledge on various topics," "building background knowledge through pre-reading activities" was the top strategy employed by 20 teachers, representing 40.00%. Additionally, the challenge of "limited home support for reading activities" is primarily addressed by "sending home reading materials and guides for parents," a strategy adopted by 70.00% of the respondents, emphasizing the importance of extending learning beyond the classroom. Moreover, in the case of "reading disabilities and special education needs," "collaborating with special education teachers for individualized plans" was the most frequently used strategy, implemented by 40.00% of the respondents to ensure responsive support for learners with special needs.

Meanwhile, as to challenges focusing on instructional factors, such as "balancing standardized test preparation with comprehension," both "focusing on critical thinking and comprehension skills" and "incorporating multimedia tools and interactive reading software" were tied as the top strategies, each employed by 30.00% of respondents to ensure that test preparation does not overshadow deep learning. Additionally, for

"inadequate assessment tools for monitoring progress," the most frequently employed strategy was "providing contextualized interventions and support for struggling readers," used by 50.00% of the respondents to ensure that struggling students receive tailored support. Lastly, for the problem of "balancing reading instruction with other curriculum demands," the most common strategy was "integrating reading instruction across the curriculum," adopted by 46.00% of respondents, ensuring that reading is a constant component of the broader curriculum.

Furthermore, in terms of primary challenges in school factors such as the problem of "insufficient funding for reading programs and resources," multiple strategies were ranked equally, with "applying for grants," "partnering with local businesses and community organizations for donations," "utilizing free or low-cost online reading resources," "requesting support from LGU and NGOs," and "conducting fund-generating activities," each being used by ten teachers, representing 20.00% of the respondents. These strategies reflect a multifaceted approach to overcoming financial constraints by seeking external support and utilizing cost-effective resources. Also, in the case of "curriculum constraints limiting flexibility in teaching methods," the highest-ranking strategy was "advocating for curriculum revisions to include more flexibility," employed by 12 teachers, representing 24.00% of the respondents. Lastly, with the challenge about "limited parental involvement and awareness in reading programs," the respondents primarily encourage parents to participate in classroom reading activities with 20 in frequency, equivalent to 40.00%.

The results generally indicate that teachers employ various adaptable, collaborative, and innovative strategies to address challenges related to student engagement, instructional demands, and school-based constraints in developing reading comprehension skills. These strategies demonstrate a proactive approach by teachers, incorporating both individualized and collective solutions to overcome diverse challenges, such as limited home support, inadequate funding, and balancing curriculum demands. The findings also highlight the need for continuous improvement and support in critical areas, such as differentiated instruction, parental involvement, and integrating technology and multimedia tools in teaching.

The results also imply that teachers need continuous adaptability and creativity in addressing the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers must continue to employ differentiated instruction and collaborate with specialists, particularly in managing reading disabilities and special education needs. Frequent strategies to engage parents, such as sending home reading materials and encouraging classroom participation, highlight teachers' critical role in bridging the gap between home and school learning. Teachers are encouraged to actively seek external resources, such as grants and partnerships, to overcome financial constraints and improve access to up-to-date reading materials and resources.

Like the current findings, related studies also emphasized that in addressing challenges related to reading comprehension, teachers employ various strategies tailored to meet individual student needs. For students facing language barriers or learning disabilities, differentiated instruction and scaffolding techniques are used to gradually

build skills and foster a growth mindset (Reyes et al., 2023; Tajeddin et al., 2020). Teachers also create supportive classroom environments where students feel comfortable seeking help and addressing emotional barriers to comprehension (Li & Peng, 2020). Instructionally, teachers adapt materials to match students' reading levels and interests, employ diverse teaching methods like interactive read-aloud, and provide explicit instruction on comprehension strategies such as summarizing and predicting (Shehzad et al., 2020; Gottshalk, 2023). They continuously assess student progress and adjust instruction to ensure success (Ghasemi, 2022). Despite challenges posed by limited school resources or professional development opportunities, teachers independently seek resources, collaborate with peers, and advocate for school policies that support literacy instruction (Ali, 2020).

Furthermore, the interview results revealed the dominating theme “**Access to Resources**” as the major coping strategy where the participants mentioned:

Participant A: "To improve reading comprehension, school administrations and the Department of Education should support teachers through professional development and access to quality resources..."

Participant B: "The school administration and the Department of Education should provide reading materials such as leveled reading books and subject-specific textbooks for instruction, as schools currently face a significant shortage of books..."

Participant C: "A major way the Department of Education can help is by allocating funds for reading materials that children can use..."

Participant D: "Ensure Access to Diverse and Engaging Reading Materials. Provide a variety of leveled books in classroom libraries to meet the diverse needs of students. Invest in high-interest, culturally relevant texts to engage reluctant readers."

Participant E: "Support initiatives like reading challenges, book clubs, and literacy festivals to promote a culture of reading. Incorporate structured reading intervention programs for struggling readers, ensuring they receive additional support."

Moreover, the qualitative data revealed that access to resources is a dominant coping strategy for improving reading comprehension instruction, as teachers rely on external support to address instructional challenges. Participant A emphasized the need for professional development and access to quality resources, suggesting that both training and materials are essential for effective teaching. Similarly, Participant B highlighted the shortage of leveled reading books and subject-specific textbooks, underscoring the necessity for schools and the Department of Education to provide adequate instructional materials. Participant C further reinforced this need, stating that allocating funds for reading materials would significantly support students' literacy development. Additionally, Participant D stressed the importance of diverse and engaging

reading materials, particularly high-interest and culturally relevant texts, to enhance student engagement. Beyond physical resources, Participant E suggested promoting literacy initiatives such as reading challenges, book clubs, and structured reading intervention programs, fostering a culture of reading within schools. These findings indicate that resource availability, professional training, and structured literacy programs are crucial coping mechanisms for improving reading comprehension outcomes.

These findings suggest that institutional support plays a critical role in enhancing reading instruction, requiring schools and educational policymakers to prioritize resource allocation and teacher development. First, investing in professional development programs ensures that teachers are equipped with the latest instructional strategies, allowing them to adapt to diverse learning needs. Second, providing leveled reading books and structured literacy programs can bridge gaps in student comprehension, ensuring that all learners have access to appropriate reading materials. Additionally, fostering a school-wide reading culture through reading festivals, book clubs, and parental involvement initiatives encourages students to develop a lifelong love for reading.

These results also are supported by Yang (2020), who argues that problem-focused coping strategies, such as resource allocation and instructional planning, help teachers navigate systemic instructional challenges effectively. Similarly, Ali (2020) emphasizes the role of emotion-focused coping strategies, including fostering a supportive school culture and engaging in literacy-based community programs, reinforcing the study's findings on the importance of collaborative reading activities and school-wide initiatives. Additionally, Ghasemi (2022) highlights the significance of adaptive coping mechanisms, supporting the idea that teachers adjust their instructional techniques, classroom management approaches, and professional training to overcome reading comprehension barriers. However, unlike Park (2022), who suggests that individual coping mechanisms, such as seeking mental health support, are essential for educators, the present study emphasizes institutional-level interventions, such as professional development, resource funding, and curriculum support, as primary coping mechanisms. This contrast suggests that while individual strategies contribute to teacher resilience, long-term solutions require systemic changes that ensure sustained access to professional training, instructional materials, and structured literacy programs to effectively support reading comprehension instruction.

Part IV. Assessment of the Significant Relationship between the Practices of Teachers and the Challenges they faced in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Table 10

Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge in Practices of Teachers and Challenges They Face in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Vocabulary Knowledge					
Challenges Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Student-Related Factors	0.270	Weak Positive	0.008	Reject Ho	Significant
Instructional Factors	0.037	Very Weak Positive	0.721	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School-Related Factors	0.282	Weak Positive	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 12 illustrates the statistical analysis of the significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge in teachers’ practices and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension. The findings indicate that student-related factors and school-related factors exhibit weak but statistically significant positive correlations with vocabulary knowledge practices, while instructional factors show no significant relationship. These results suggest that vocabulary knowledge practices are influenced by both student-related and school-related challenges, but not necessarily by instructional constraints.

Moreover, a weak positive correlation (0.270, $p = 0.008$) was observed between student-related factors and vocabulary knowledge practices, indicating that as student-related challenges increase (e.g., lack of motivation, limited prior knowledge, or reading engagement difficulties), teachers tend to adjust their vocabulary instruction. Since the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming a significant relationship. Similarly, school-related factors showed a weak positive correlation (0.282, $p = 0.006$), which also led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding suggests that external school-related difficulties, such as inadequate reading materials, lack of administrative support, or rigid curricular constraints, influence how teachers approach vocabulary instruction. In contrast, instructional factors exhibited a very weak positive correlation (0.037, $p = 0.721$), indicating no significant relationship. The p-value is well above 0.05, leading to the failure to reject the null hypothesis, implying that teachers’

vocabulary instruction practices are not directly impacted by instructional constraints such as time limitations, class size, or access to teaching resources.

The findings imply that student-related and school-related challenges are significant factors in shaping teachers' vocabulary instruction. Teachers may be adapting their vocabulary teaching strategies in response to students' difficulties with word recognition, comprehension, and engagement. Additionally, school-related constraints, such as limited funding for books and lack of professional development, may push teachers to modify their instructional strategies. However, the lack of a significant relationship with instructional factors suggests that teachers maintain a consistent approach to vocabulary instruction despite classroom constraints, possibly due to their reliance on structured teaching strategies that remain stable regardless of environmental difficulties.

This also confirm the findings of Li & Clariana (2019) that reading proficiency is highly dependent on vocabulary knowledge, reinforcing the notion that student-related challenges, such as motivation and engagement, directly impact vocabulary instruction. The results also align with Hudson (2021) and Karbla et al. (2021), who stress that pre-reading vocabulary instruction and active engagement strategies are essential for overcoming student comprehension barriers. However, Schult et al. (2022) reported that instructional constraints, such as limited class time, can hinder effective vocabulary teaching, which contrasts with the current study's finding that instructional factors do not significantly influence teachers' vocabulary practices. Additionally, Kiew & Shah (2020) argue that school-related constraints, including outdated curriculum and limited resources, negatively affect vocabulary instruction, which supports the significant relationship found between school-related factors and vocabulary knowledge practices in this study.

Table 11

Significant Relationship Between Text Comprehension in Practices of Teachers and Challenges They Face in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Text Comprehension					
Challenges Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Student-Related Factors	0.209	Weak Positive	0.040	Reject Ho	Significant
Instructional Factors	0.000	No Correlation	1.000	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

School-Related Factors	0.194	Very Weak Positive	0.570	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
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Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 11 exhibits the statistical analysis of the significant relationship between text comprehension practices of teachers and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension. The findings reveal that student-related factors exhibit a weak but significant positive correlation with text comprehension practices, while instructional and school-related factors show no significant relationship with teachers' approaches to text comprehension. These indicate that student-related difficulties influence how teachers approach text comprehension instruction, whereas broader instructional and school-related factors do not have a measurable impact.

Additionally, weak positive correlation (0.209, $p = 0.040$) was observed between student-related factors and text comprehension practices, indicating that as challenges related to students' motivation, reading ability, or prior knowledge increase, teachers adjust their strategies for text comprehension instruction. Since the p-value is below 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming a significant relationship. However, instructional factors showed no correlation (0.000, $p = 1.000$), indicating that factors such as instructional time, class size, or access to teaching resources do not significantly affect how teachers teach text comprehension. With a p-value far above 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Similarly, school-related factors exhibited a very weak positive correlation (0.194, $p = 0.570$), which is not statistically significant, suggesting that challenges such as lack of funding do not play a significant role in shaping teachers' text comprehension instruction.

These research results imply that student-related difficulties, such as low engagement, lack of foundational skills, and limited vocabulary, push teachers to modify their instructional strategies to accommodate student needs. This aligns with the notion that teachers often adapt comprehension strategies to address the varying abilities of learners, focusing on scaffolding and differentiated instruction. Meanwhile, the lack of correlation with instructional and school-related factors suggests that teachers maintain consistent text comprehension strategies regardless of external constraints. This could be due to structured reading instruction frameworks that ensure comprehension is a core component of literacy education, regardless of available resources or time constraints.

This also conforms the research of Hudson (2021) and Karbla et al. (2021) that text comprehension is highly influenced by student motivation and background knowledge, supporting the significant relationship between student-related factors and text comprehension practices found in this study. Furthermore, Schult et al. (2022) highlight that reading comprehension strategies must be tailored to address student difficulties, particularly in decoding and meaning-making, reinforcing the current findings. However, the study's result that instructional factors do not significantly impact text comprehension instruction contradicts Lacerna & Revilla (2022), who argue that limited

instructional time can negatively affect reading comprehension teaching. Additionally, Hwang and Duke (2020) found that school-related constraints, such as outdated curriculum and insufficient professional development, impede comprehension instruction, which contrasts with this study's findings that school factors do not have a significant impact. These comparisons explicitly show that while teachers adapt text comprehension strategies based on student difficulties, they appear resilient to instructional and school-related constraints, maintaining structured comprehension instruction despite external challenges.

Table 12

Significant Relationship Between Finding the Main Ideas in Practices of Teachers and Challenges They Face in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Finding the Main Idea					
Challenges Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Student-Related Factors	0.290	Moderate Positive	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Instructional Factors	0.085	Very Weak Positive	0.413	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School Related Factors	0.257	Weak Positive	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 12 illustrates the statistical analysis of the significant relationship between finding the main idea practices of teachers and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension. The results revealed that student-related factors and school-related factors have a significant positive relationship with teachers' main idea instruction, while instructional factors do not significantly impact teachers' practices. This suggests that students' challenges and school-related constraints influence how teachers approach finding the main idea instruction, whereas broader instructional factors do not have a measurable effect.

Additionally, moderate positive correlation (0.290, $p = 0.004$) was found between student-related factors and finding the main idea practices, indicating that as students face greater difficulties in reading comprehension, such as weak analytical skills, lack of background knowledge, and motivation issues, teachers tend to modify their strategies to help students identify key points in a text more effectively. Since the p-value is below

0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming a statistically significant relationship. Similarly, school-related factors exhibited a weak positive correlation (0.257, $p = 0.011$), meaning that institutional constraints such as lack of reading resources, rigid curricula, or inadequate teacher training also affect how teachers implement main idea instruction. The null hypothesis was rejected, confirming significance. On the other hand, instructional factors had a very weak positive correlation (0.085, $p = 0.413$), indicating no significant relationship. The null hypothesis was not rejected, suggesting that issues like class size, lesson planning, or instructional time do not heavily impact how teachers teach finding the main idea.

Moreover, the findings imply that student-related challenges significantly shape how teachers approach teaching the main idea. Teachers likely adopt scaffolding strategies, guided questioning, and explicit instruction to help students recognize central ideas in a text, particularly when students struggle with comprehension and critical thinking. Additionally, the significant influence of school-related factors suggests that teachers' ability to effectively teach main idea identification may be constrained by school policies, curriculum limitations, or the availability of teaching resources. On the other hand, the lack of a significant relationship with instructional factors implies that teachers may implement main idea strategies consistently, regardless of external instructional constraints, possibly due to the structured nature of reading comprehension instruction.

Similar with the current findings, Shelton et al. (2021) also found that explicit instruction in identifying main ideas is crucial for students with reading difficulties, supporting the significant relationship between student-related factors and main idea instruction in this study. Similarly, Hudson (2021) found that students' motivation and prior knowledge are key determinants of their ability to identify main ideas, reinforcing the results. However, the study contrasts with Lacerna & Revilla (2022), who argue that instructional factors such as time limitations and class sizes can restrict how well teachers can implement structured main idea instruction, while the current findings indicate no significant impact.

Table 13

Significant Relationship Between Answering Questions in Practices of Teachers and Challenges They Face in Teaching Reading Comprehension

Answering Questions					
Challenges Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Student-Related Factors	0.122	Very Weak Positive	0.234	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Instructional Factors	0.040	Very Weak Positive	0.701	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School Factors Related	0.082	Very Weak Positive	0.427	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject H_0 , otherwise failed to reject H_0 .”

Table 13 presents the statistical analysis of the significant relationship between answering questions practices of teachers and the challenges they face in teaching reading comprehension. The results reveal that student-related, instructional, and school-related factors all show very weak positive correlations with answering questions strategies, and none of these relationships are statistically significant. This suggests that challenges in these areas do not strongly influence how teachers implement questioning techniques in reading comprehension instruction.

Further, the correlation coefficients indicate that student-related factors (0.122, $p = 0.234$), instructional factors (0.040, $p = 0.701$), and school-related factors (0.082, $p = 0.427$) all exhibit very weak positive relationships with answering questions practices. Since the p -values for all three variables exceed the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis is not rejected, confirming that these challenges do not significantly impact teachers' questioning strategies. This suggests that teachers maintain a consistent approach to using questioning techniques, regardless of variations in student challenges, instructional constraints, or school-related issues.

These indicate that questioning strategies are a core, stable component of reading comprehension instruction. Unlike other comprehension strategies that may require more adaptability, questioning techniques are likely embedded into teaching routines and consistently applied across different classroom settings. The lack of significant relationships with student-related factors suggests that teachers implement questioning strategies systematically, regardless of students' motivation levels, prior knowledge, or comprehension difficulties. Similarly, the lack of significant correlation with instructional factors indicates that teachers do not adjust their questioning techniques based on class sizes, curriculum constraints, or available teaching resources. Furthermore, the lack of impact from school-related factors suggests that teachers continue to prioritize questioning as a critical instructional tool, even in the face of administrative or policy-related challenges.

Same with the current results, Diana & Sepyanda (2022) also argue that explicit instruction in answering different types of comprehension questions—literal, inferential, and evaluative—can significantly impact students' reading skills, reinforcing the importance of consistent questioning strategies in teaching. However, Ballakrishnan & Mohamad (2020) emphasize that engaging question-based learning is highly dependent on instructional conditions, such as student-teacher interaction and classroom

environment, which contradicts the current study's findings that instructional factors do not significantly influence questioning strategies. Additionally, Rahayu et al. (2023) highlight that students often struggle with inferential questions and require additional instructional support, suggesting that while questioning techniques are widely practiced, they may still need adaptation to address students' specific comprehension difficulties. Meanwhile, Hudson (2021) found that questioning strategies are one of the most effective ways to promote deep comprehension, making them a staple in reading instruction regardless of external constraints, which aligns with the results of this study.

Part V. Proposed Policy Recommendations for Instructional Support Based on the Findings of the Study

Proposed Policy Recommendations for Instructional Support Based on the Findings of the Study

Based on the study's findings, a policy recommendation titled "Enhancing Instructional Support for Reading Comprehension Development in Elementary Schools: A Policy Recommendation Based on the Study of Practices, Challenges, and Coping Strategies in the General Luna District, Division of Quezon" is proposed. This is designed to improve teaching practices, address challenges, and provide instructional support for developing reading comprehension among elementary learners in the General Luna District, Division of Quezon. Based on the study's key findings, the proposed policy focuses on enhancing current instructional approaches, tackling student-related, instructional, and school-related challenges, and implementing effective coping strategies to support teachers and ensure that learners develop strong reading comprehension skills.

Moreover, regarding teaching practices, the policy recommends several vital strategies. For vocabulary knowledge, teachers will receive training on effectively creating and monitoring vocabulary journals, helping reinforce students' vocabulary retention. Regarding text comprehension, the policy suggests providing professional development on summarization techniques and incorporating these techniques into cross-curricular lesson plans. Standardized worksheets and instructional guidelines will be developed and applied across grade levels to improve instruction in finding the main idea. Additionally, peer-questioning sessions will be encouraged to promote collaborative learning, with teachers being trained to moderate these activities effectively. Similarly, at its core, the policy seeks to enhance teacher practices by offering targeted professional development and training in vocabulary instruction, summarization techniques, and strategies for finding the main idea.

Additionally, the policy addresses various challenges teachers face in teaching reading comprehension, and the proposed policies are based on the commonly applied coping strategies by the teachers. For student-related factors such as attention and concentration issues, teachers will be provided with interactive and engaging reading resources tailored to different reading levels. Pre-reading strategies will be emphasized to tackle limited background knowledge, equipping teachers with the tools to enhance

students' comprehension of upcoming material. The policy recognizes the need to support reading development outside the classroom by regularly distributing home reading guides and materials to parents. For students with reading disabilities, the policy proposes formalizing collaboration between general and special education teachers to ensure individualized support for these learners.

Moreover, instructional challenges, such as balancing reading instruction with other curriculum demands, will be addressed through a district-wide initiative to integrate reading comprehension tasks into non-language arts subjects, supported by professional training and lesson plan development. Lastly, the policy acknowledges the need for greater parental involvement in reading programs. To address this, strategies will be implemented to increase parental participation in classroom reading sessions and school events, fostering a more collaborative and supportive learning environment for students.

This policy recommendation provides a comprehensive approach to improving reading comprehension in the General Luna District. In enhancing teacher practices, providing necessary resources, and engaging parents, the proposed strategies aim to create a more supportive, inclusive, and effective educational environment that enhances learners' reading comprehension outcomes. This, in turn, will not only enhance students' reading comprehension skills but also contribute to their broader academic success and long-term learning outcomes for learners inclusively in the context of General Luna.

Conclusions

Based on the presented findings, the study arrived at the following conclusions:

1. In teaching reading comprehension, the teachers showed varying level of practices where vocabulary knowledge is highly practiced with the use of flashcards and routine activities, text comprehension is highly practiced with engaging in read-aloud sessions and the use of question-based comprehension practices, finding the main idea is also highly practiced using visual aids and identifying key details, and teachers answering questions is also highly practiced through the use of “Wh” questions and active questioning practices.
2. The teachers faced highly challenging factors related to students, instruction, and the school where student-related factors such as attention issues, limited background knowledge, lack of reading support, and special education needs along with lack of student motivation and focus. Additionally, they also encountered highly challenging instructional factors due to balancing reading instruction with curriculum demands, standardized test preparation, and limited reading time along with learners' diversity. Finally, teachers experienced highly challenging school-related factors involving low parental involvement, curriculum constraints, and inadequate funding for reading programs and resources along with curriculum changes.
3. To address the challenges, the teachers implement strategies such as interactive reading activities, prereading activities, and home reading materials for student-related challenges. To address instructional factors, they use multimedia tools,

contextualized interventions, and curriculum integration. In response to school factors, teachers secure grants, advocate curriculum revision, and encourage parental involvement. Teachers further acknowledge having full access to resources as key coping mechanisms.

4. Teachers' practices in teaching reading comprehension, in terms of vocabulary knowledge (Ho₁) and finding the main ideas (Ho₄) are rejected showing significant relationship to student-related factors and school factors. Meanwhile, text comprehension (Ho₃) has a significant relationship with student-related factors that also rejected the hypothesis. However, teaching practice in answering questions in (Ho₄) was accepted and has no significant relationship with the identified challenges.
5. A Policy Recommendation titled "Enhancing Instructional Support for Reading Comprehension Development in Elementary Schools: A Policy Recommendation Based on the Study of Practices, Challenges, and Coping Strategies in the General Luna District, Division of Quezon" is proposed based on the research findings.

Recommendations

Based on the determined research conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. Given that teachers demonstrate strong practices in reading comprehension instruction—particularly in answering questions, vocabulary knowledge, and text comprehension—but continue to face notable challenges, it is recommended that DepEd policymakers develop targeted policies to support teachers. These policies should focus on specialized training programs to help teachers support learners with special needs, enhance parental involvement in literacy activities at home, and provide adequate instructional materials. Increased funding for multimedia resources and contextualized learning materials should also be prioritized to strengthen students' background knowledge and comprehension skills.
2. As teachers struggle to balance reading instruction with curriculum demands and address diverse learner needs, DepEd officials should implement teacher development programs focused on differentiated instruction and inclusive teaching strategies. These programs should equip educators with skills to support students of varying abilities, including those with special needs. Additionally, curricular support programs should be reinforced to ensure that reading comprehension remains a priority across subject areas.
3. While highly practiced strategies such as vocabulary development and identifying main ideas are effective, they remain closely tied to student-related challenges, including limited background knowledge and parental support. Therefore, teachers should continue strengthening these strategies while also exploring new, student-centered approaches that address these learning barriers. Additionally, increased parent-teacher collaboration is recommended to create extended reading support systems at home, ensuring that literacy instruction continues beyond the classroom environment.
4. Since students' comprehension development is significantly influenced by their engagement in vocabulary-building and comprehension activities, learners should

be encouraged to actively participate in structured literacy programs utilizing multimedia tools and digital reading resources. Teachers and parents should collaborate in providing targeted support, ensuring that students receive consistent reading reinforcement both in school and at home. Implementing interactive and student-led reading activities can also enhance motivation and improve comprehension outcomes.

5. While this study established strong relationships between teaching practices and instructional challenges, further research is needed to explore additional instructional strategies and their long-term effects on reading comprehension. Future researchers should investigate the impact of multimedia integration on reading comprehension development, particularly for students with special needs and those with limited background knowledge. Additionally, further studies should examine the role of parental involvement in literacy development, identifying effective models for integrating home and school reading interventions to enhance student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research principles to ensure the protection and confidentiality of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before data collection, ensuring their voluntary participation. Participants were assured of their anonymity, and all personal information was kept strictly confidential. The data collected was used solely for academic purposes, with findings presented objectively and without bias. Additionally, ethical guidelines were followed in the handling, analysis, and reporting of data to maintain the integrity of the research. The study also complied with institutional and educational research standards to uphold fairness, transparency, and respect for all individuals involved.

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